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Profilaxis de los efectos cardiacos y sociales en pacientes con diabetes mellitus

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Abstract

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is one of the leading risk factors for the development of cardiovascular diseases (CVD), which significantly worsens the prognosis and quality of life of patients. Prevention of cardiovascular complications in patients with diabetes includes a set of measures aimed at reducing blood glucose levels, normalising blood pressure, improving lipid metabolism and preventing microvascular disorders. Important aspects are early diagnosis, regular health monitoring, and the use of pharmacotherapy such as angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors, statins and other drugs.

Lifestyle changes, including dietary modification, physical activity, smoking cessation and weight control, are equally important. Teaching patients to self-monitor, informing them about risks and the importance of adherence to recommendations also play a key role in preventing complications. Timely diagnosis and prevention of cardiovascular diseases can significantly reduce mortality and morbidity in patients with diabetes.

Key words: diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular diseases, prevention, arterial hypertension, hypercholesterolemia, hyperglycaemia.

Resumen

La diabetes mellitus (DM) es uno de los principales factores de riesgo para el desarrollo de enfermedades cardiovasculares (ECV), que empeora significativamente el pronóstico y la calidad de vida de los pacientes. La prevención de las complicaciones cardiovasculares en pacientes con diabetes incluye un conjunto de medidas encaminadas a reducir los niveles de glucosa en sangre, normalizar la presión arterial, mejorar el metabolismo lipídico y prevenir los trastornos microvasculares. Aspectos importantes son el diagnóstico precoz, el seguimiento regular de la salud y el uso de farmacoterapia como inhibidores de la enzima convertidora de angiotensina (ECA), estatinas y otros fármacos.

Los cambios en el estilo de vida, incluyendo la modificación de la dieta, la actividad física, el abandono del hábito de fumar y el control del peso, son igualmente importantes. Enseñar a los pacientes a autocontrolarse, informarles sobre los riesgos y la importancia de la adherencia a las recomendaciones también desempeñan un papel clave en la prevención de complicaciones. El diagnóstico y la prevención oportunos de las enfermedades cardiovasculares pueden reducir significativamente la mortalidad y la morbilidad en pacientes con diabetes.

Palabras clave: diabetes mellitus, enfermedades cardiovasculares, prevención, hipertensión arterial, hipercolesterolemia, hiperglucemia.

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is one of the most common chronic diseases in the world, significantly increasing the risk of various complications, including cardiovascular disease (CVD)¹. Patients with diabetes have several times higher risk of myocardial infarction, stroke and other cardiovascular diseases compared to the population without diabetes. This is due to a number of metabolic abnormalities such as hyperglycaemia, dyslipidaemia, insulin resistance and chronic inflammation, which play a key role in the progression of atherosclerosis and other vascular diseases.

Timely prevention of cardiovascular complications in diabetic patients is essential to reduce mortality and morbidity and to improve quality of life. Modern approaches include not only drug therapy aimed at controlling blood sugar, blood pressure and lipid metabolism, but also lifestyle correction, including diet, physical activity and avoidance of bad habits. The most important aspect is to educate patients in self-control and prevention of risks associated with cardiovascular diseases.

The aim of this study is to review the main methods of prevention of cardiovascular complications in patients with diabetes mellitus, to identify the most effective approaches and strategies to improve clinical outcomes in this group of patients.

Materials and methods

In the process of writing this article, a number of research methods were applied within the framework of studying the peculiarities of cardiovascular complications prevention in patients with diabetes mellitus. Thus, a systematic review and analysis of existing scientific publications, clinical guidelines and studies on the topic of cardiovascular diseases in diabetes, which allowed us to generalise and synthesise knowledge about the pathogenesis, prevention and treatment of such complications. Comparison of different methods of cardiovascular disease prevention in diabetic patients, such as pharmacotherapy, lifestyle modification, use of

new technologies and interventions made it possible to highlight the most effective approaches.

Through the collection and statistical analysis of data from various studies to identify the most significant risk factors and effective methods to prevent cardiovascular complications in diabetic patients, general trends were identified and evidence for recommendations was reasonably presented.

By analysing practical experience and clinical cases based on the results of observation and treatment of patients with diabetes, including their susceptibility to cardiovascular disease, the association between diabetes and CVD risks was identified, and the effectiveness of preventive measures was evaluated.

The use of these methods made it possible to comprehensively consider the problem of prevention of cardiovascular complications in patients with diabetes mellitus and on the basis of theoretical analysis to offer practical recommendations to improve clinical practice.

Results

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is indeed one of the key risk factors for cardiovascular disease (CVD), as the chronically elevated blood glucose levels characteristic of diabetes promote atherosclerosis, vascular damage and increased likelihood of blood clots². Diabetic patients are more likely to suffer from hypertension, dyslipidaemia and inflammation, which also significantly increases the risk of CVDs such as myocardial infarction, stroke and peripheral arterial disease.

In addition, the presence of diabetes accelerates the progression of vascular disorders, which can lead to a more severe course of cardiovascular disease, which adversely affects the quality of life, reducing physical activity, performance and psychological state of patients³. The prognosis of such patients can significantly worsen in case of insufficient prevention and timely control of sugar levels, blood pressure and other risk factors. Thus, control and prevention of cardiovascular disease in patients with diabetes mellitus are crucial to improve the health and prolong the life of these patients.

Prevention of cardiovascular complications in diabetic patients requires a comprehensive approach and includes several key areas (Table 1).

Table 1. Key interventions to prevent cardiovascular complications in diabetic patients

Area of prevention	Activities	Objective
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - prescription of hypoglycaemic drugs (insulin, metformin, sulphonylureas, etc.) - dietary correction (reduction of simple carbohydrates) - increased physical activity - use of antihypertensive drugs (ACE inhibitors, ARBs, diuretics, beta-blockers) - regular blood monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - maintenance of normoglycaemia - prevention of diabetic complications
Reduction of blood glucose levels		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintaining normal blood pressure - reducing the risk of cardiovascular disease and kidney complications
Normalisation of blood pressure Improvement of lipid metabolism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - prescription of statins or other drugs to normalise cholesterol and triglyceride levels - dietary correction (reduction of saturated fat intake) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lowering blood cholesterol levels - preventing atherosclerosis and cardiovascular diseases
Prevention of microvascular disorders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - glucose and blood pressure monitoring - regular monitoring of the eyes, kidneys and nervous system - use of antioxidants and anti-inflammatory drugs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - prevention of retinopathy, nephropathy and neuropathy - protecting small blood vessels from damage and improving the general condition of the body

Reducing blood glucose levels is the main focus of prevention of cardiovascular complications in patients with diabetes mellitus. Chronically elevated blood glucose levels contribute to vascular damage, deterioration of microcirculation and accelerate the process of atherosclerosis, which, in turn, increases the risk of myocardial infarction, stroke and other cardiovascular diseases[3].

Both drug and non-drug methods are used to control blood glucose levels. Medications include insulin and oral hypoglycaemic drugs such as metformin, sulphonylureas, DPP-4 inhibitors and glucagon-like peptides. These drugs help to normalise blood sugar levels by improving insulin sensitivity or stimulating insulin release⁴.

However, along with drug therapy, considerable attention is paid to lifestyle correction. Nutrition plays an important role in glucose control⁵. Diabetic patients are advised to

reduce the intake of simple carbohydrates (sugars) and increase fibre intake to improve sugar control. A diet with a low glycaemic index helps to avoid sudden fluctuations in glucose levels.

In addition, physical activity is key to glucose control. Regular physical activity, such as walking, swimming or aerobic exercise, helps to improve insulin sensitivity, reduce weight and normalise metabolism⁶. Body weight control is also important, as overweight directly affects blood glucose levels and may contribute to the development of insulin resistance.

Thus, a comprehensive approach, including both drug treatment and lifestyle changes, is the basis for effective glucose control in diabetic patients, which, in turn, contributes to reducing the risk of cardiovascular disease and improving the quality of life of patients.

Normalisation of blood pressure is an important element in the prevention of cardiovascular complications in patients with diabetes mellitus. High blood pressure (hypertension) significantly increases the risk of atherosclerosis, myocardial infarction, stroke, and kidney and eye damage⁷. In diabetic patients, hypertension is most often found in combination with other risk factors such as dyslipidaemia and elevated blood glucose levels, making effective blood pressure control essential.

Antihypertensive drugs are used to normalise blood pressure in diabetic patients⁸. Angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors and angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs), which not only reduce blood pressure but also have a protective effect on the kidneys, are the most effective in this group of patients. These drugs help to reduce microvascular damage and reduce the risk of diabetic nephropathy, which is one of the most serious complications of diabetes. Diuretics, beta-blockers and calcium antagonists are also commonly used and may be used depending on the patient's condition and comorbidities⁹.

In addition, blood pressure can be controlled through lifestyle changes. It is recommended to reduce salt intake, improve diet quality, avoid bad habits (e.g. smoking) and follow a physical activity regime¹⁰. Regular physical activity, such as aerobic exercise, can help reduce blood pressure and improve heart and vascular function.

It is important that diabetic patients regularly monitor blood pressure and follow the doctor's recommendations for the treatment of hypertension¹¹. It should be remembered that normalisation of blood pressure can significantly reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease, improve the function of organs and systems, and improve the quality of life of the patient.

Improvement of lipid metabolism plays an important role in the prevention of cardiovascular disease in patients with diabetes mellitus. Dyslipidaemia, i.e. disturbance of the normal ratio of lipids (fats) in the blood, is one of the

main risk factors for atherosclerosis, which can lead to myocardial infarction, stroke and other serious cardiovascular diseases¹². Diabetic patients often have high levels of total cholesterol, triglycerides and low levels of high-density lipoprotein (HDL), which exacerbates the risk of cardiovascular complications.

One of the main methods of lipid metabolism correction is the use of hypolipidaemic drugs, especially statins. Statins effectively reduce total cholesterol as well as low-density lipoprotein (LDL) levels, which is considered «bad» cholesterol that contributes to the formation of atherosclerotic plaques¹³. Statins also help to reduce inflammation in vascular walls and stabilise existing atherosclerotic plaques, which reduces the risk of plaque rupture and blood clots.

In addition, it is important to control triglyceride levels in diabetic patients, as elevated levels also contribute to the development of atherosclerosis¹⁴. In addition to statin therapy, fibrates and preparations containing omega-3 fatty acids can be used to help reduce triglyceride levels in the blood.

One of the most important aspects of dyslipidaemia prevention is dietary intervention. Diabetic patients are advised to reduce their intake of saturated and trans fats and increase their intake of healthy monounsaturated and polyunsaturated fats such as olive oil, nuts and fish rich in omega-3 fatty acids¹⁵. Keeping the body hydrated, avoiding alcohol and smoking also helps to improve lipid metabolism.

Regular monitoring of cholesterol and triglyceride levels, as well as adequate pharmacotherapy and lifestyle changes, can significantly reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease in diabetic patients, improving overall prognosis and quality of life.

Prevention of microvascular abnormalities is an integral part of preventing cardiovascular complications in patients with diabetes mellitus¹⁶. Microvascular complications such as diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy and neuropathy develop due to prolonged exposure of small blood vessels to elevated glucose levels, resulting in their damage. These complications can significantly reduce the quality of life of patients and can also cause serious conditions such as blindness, kidney failure and loss of sensation in the limbs.

To prevent microvascular damage, strict blood glucose and blood pressure control are key¹⁷. Maintaining normoglycaemia helps prevent vascular damage, and controlling blood pressure reduces the risk of kidney and eye damage. It is important for diabetic patients to monitor their sugar levels regularly and undergo screening to detect signs of retinopathy, nephropathy and neuropathy early.

In addition, the use of medications aimed at vascular protection is an important element of prevention. For example, angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors

and angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs) not only normalise blood pressure but also have a protective effect on the kidneys and small vessels. Statins, which lower cholesterol levels, also help to reduce inflammation in the vascular walls and prevent the progression of atherosclerosis.

Early detection of microvascular complications and their timely treatment with medication, laser therapy or other methods can significantly slow down their development and prevent severe consequences. For this purpose, patients with diabetes are recommended regular eye examinations (examination by an ophthalmologist), kidney function tests (albumin level in urine) and sensitivity testing in the extremities. Following these recommendations helps not only to prevent microvascular complications but also to reduce the overall risk of cardiovascular disease in diabetic patients.

Discussion

Early diagnosis, regular health monitoring and the use of pharmacotherapy are integral elements in the prevention of cardiovascular complications in diabetic patients. Such measures can effectively control risks and prevent the development of serious diseases such as myocardial infarction, stroke, as well as nephropathy and retinopathy.

Early diagnosis of cardiovascular disease and microvascular complications in diabetic patients allows for early detection of the problem when it can be controlled or prevented. Regular check-ups, including blood tests for sugar, cholesterol, triglycerides, and blood pressure monitoring, are important measures to detect changes in a patient's condition in a timely manner. In addition, regular eye examinations by an ophthalmologist and kidney function tests can help detect retinopathy and nephropathy so that treatment can be started in time¹⁸.

Continuous monitoring of a diabetic patient allows you to respond quickly to changes in your health. This includes regular measurement of blood glucose levels, blood pressure, and tests for cholesterol and other lipids. Diabetic patients should also monitor their body weight, as being overweight is an additional risk factor for cardiovascular disease. It is essential that the patient checks these indicators regularly, independently and in co-operation with the physician, in order not to miss early signs of complications.

To prevent cardiovascular disease in diabetic patients, the use of pharmacotherapy is an important element. Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACE inhibitor drugs such as lisinopril and ramipril not only help to re-

duce blood pressure but also have a protective effect on the kidneys, which is particularly important for patients with diabetic nephropathy¹⁹. ACE inhibitors help to reduce the progression of atherosclerosis and reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease.

Drugs such as atorvastatin and simvastatin are used to lower cholesterol levels, especially low-density lipoprotein (LDL), which are the main culprits of atherosclerosis. Statins help reduce inflammation in blood vessel walls, stabilise atherosclerotic plaques and reduce the risk of heart attacks and strokes.

In addition to ACE inhibitors and statins, antiaggregants (e.g. aspirin), antihypertensives (diuretics, beta-blockers, calcium antagonists), and drugs to normalise blood sugar levels (e.g. metformin, insulin and others) may be prescribed to treat diabetics with cardiovascular disease. All these drugs help to reduce the risk of complications in combination.

Thus, early diagnosis, regular health monitoring and timely use of pharmacotherapy are the main measures that help to effectively prevent cardiovascular complications in patients with diabetes mellitus.

Lifestyle modification plays a key role in preventing cardiovascular complications in diabetic patients. These measures help to significantly reduce the risks and improve the overall prognosis of the disease. A healthy diet is the foundation for controlling blood glucose levels and maintaining normal cardiovascular health. Diabetic patients are advised to follow a low glycaemic index diet, which helps in maintaining stable blood sugar levels. Basic dietary guidelines include:

- reducing the intake of simple carbohydrates (sugars) such as sugary drinks, confectionery and white bread, which cause rapid fluctuations in glucose levels;

- hydrating the body and reducing salt intake to maintain normal blood pressure;

- increasing fibre intake (vegetables, fruits, whole grain products), which helps regulate sugar levels and improves the digestive system²⁰.

Balancing the intake of healthy fats such as monounsaturated and polyunsaturated fats (e.g. olive oil, fish, nuts), which help normalise cholesterol levels and maintain vascular health.

Regular physical activity is of great importance for diabetic patients as it helps to improve insulin sensitivity, control blood sugar levels, reduce body weight and strengthen the cardiovascular system. It is recommended that diabetic patients engage in moderate physical activity for at least 150 minutes per week, which includes:

- walking, swimming, cycling or aerobic exercise;
- exercises to improve flexibility and strengthen muscles, such as yoga or strength training.

Physical activity helps to lower blood sugar levels, normalise blood pressure, improve the lipid profile (lower “bad” cholesterol) and promote general wellbeing.

Smoking is one of the most powerful risk factors for cardiovascular disease, including myocardial infarction, stroke and peripheral arterial disease. It accelerates atherosclerosis, damages blood vessel walls, reduces oxygen supply to tissues and impairs metabolism. Smoking cessation significantly reduces the risk of cardiovascular diseases and contributes to the restoration of normal functioning of blood vessels and heart.

Overweight and obesity are significant risk factors for cardiovascular disease and diabetes. Reducing body weight, even by 5-10%, can significantly improve blood sugar control, lower blood pressure, improve lipid profiles and reduce the strain on the heart. To do this, it is important to follow a calorie-controlled diet, engage in physical activity and avoid unhealthy habits. Controlling body weight helps to improve insulin sensitivity and reduce the risk of diabetes complications²¹.

As a result, lifestyle changes that include proper nutrition, physical activity, smoking cessation and weight control are an essential component of cardiovascular disease prevention in diabetic patients and significantly improve quality of life, as well as contribute to slowing disease progression.

Patient self-management education and risk communication play an important role in the prevention of cardiovascular complications in patients with diabetes. One of the key aspects of successful disease management is the active involvement of the patient in the management of their condition, which contributes to better adherence, improved well-being and reduced risk of complications.

Patient education should cover several important topics. Firstly, it includes knowledge about diabetes mellitus, its types, mechanisms of development and possible complications. It is important that patients understand how hyperglycaemia and other factors (e.g. hypertension, dyslipidaemia) can contribute to the development of cardiovascular disease. Patients should also be taught the basics of self-monitoring: regular measurement of blood glucose levels, blood pressure, and body weight monitoring.

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dyslipidaemia) can contribute to the development of cardiovascular disease. Patients should also be taught the basics of self-monitoring: regular measurement of blood glucose levels, blood pressure, and body weight monitoring.

Secondly, patients should be told how a healthy lifestyle helps to reduce their risks. This includes recommendations for healthy eating, physical activity, smoking cessation and moderate alcohol consumption. Regular physical activity such as walking, swimming or low-impact exercise can help lower blood sugar levels and improve overall vascular health²².

In addition, patient motivation is an important aspect. Self-monitoring and awareness promote a more responsible attitude towards their condition and taking the necessary steps to prevent complications. Therefore, it is important that physicians not only provide patients with information, but also regularly keep them motivated and help to adjust the treatment strategy if necessary.

Awareness of risks such as high glucose levels, hypertension, high cholesterol and triglycerides will help patients understand the importance of regular medical care and adherence to treatment. Risk assessment and timely intervention significantly improve prognosis and help prevent severe cardiovascular disease.

Thus, education and active involvement of patients in treatment and prevention is an integral part of a comprehensive programme to prevent cardiovascular complications in diabetes mellitus.

Timely diagnosis and prevention of cardiovascular diseases are the basis for a significant reduction in mortality and morbidity among patients with diabetes mellitus. Diabetes mellitus is one of the key risk factors for the development of cardiovascular diseases such as myocardial infarction, stroke, heart failure, and various microvascular complications, including retinopathy and nephropathy. The above-mentioned diseases significantly worsen the quality of life of patients and lead to increased hospitalisations and disability.

Early diagnosis helps detect cardiovascular disease in its early stages, allowing treatment to begin before the disease reaches a critical stage. Regular check-ups, including blood glucose measurement, blood pressure monitoring, cholesterol and other lipid analyses, as well as checking the condition of blood vessels and the heart, allow doctors to detect signs of cardiovascular disorders in time to start the necessary therapeutic interventions. Early detection of diseases significantly improves the prognosis and increases the effectiveness of treatment.

Health monitoring and compliance with doctor's recommendations play a key role in the prevention of cardiovascular diseases. Patients with diabetes mellitus should actively participate in the treatment process, undergo regular medical examinations and comply with doctor's

prescriptions. This contributes to better overall health, fewer complications and a reduced risk of early mortality.

Thus, timely diagnosis and prevention of cardiovascular diseases in diabetic patients are of great importance to reduce morbidity and mortality. These measures will not only improve the quality of life of patients, but also significantly reduce the burden on the health care system, increasing the effectiveness of treatment and preventing the development of severe complications.

Conclusions

Diabetes mellitus is a major factor contributing to the development of diseases such as myocardial infarction, stroke, heart failure and atherosclerosis. This requires a comprehensive approach to prevention aimed at reducing all possible risks. Early diagnosis and regular health monitoring of diabetic patients is essential for the timely detection of cardiovascular disease and microvascular complications. This allows effective control of disease progression and early treatment, which significantly improves prognosis and reduces the likelihood of serious consequences.

Control of blood glucose levels, blood pressure and lipid metabolism is the basis for the prevention of cardiovascular disease in diabetics. Regular use of pharmacotherapy (ACE inhibitors, statins, antihypertensive drugs) and lifestyle changes (healthy diet, physical activity, smoking cessation and body weight control) contribute to improving the patient's general condition and reducing the level of risk.

Lifestyle changes (diet, physical activity, avoidance of bad habits) play a crucial role in reducing the risks of cardiovascular disease and diabetes complications. These measures, along with medication, provide a significant improvement in disease control and prevent the progression of complications.

Patient education on self-management and information on cardiovascular disease risks helps to increase patients' awareness and responsibility for their health. This promotes more active participation in the treatment process and adherence to medical recommendations.

A comprehensive approach, including diagnosis, drug treatment and lifestyle changes, is the most effective way to prevent cardiovascular complications in patients with diabetes. This approach helps not only to reduce morbidity and mortality, but also to improve the quality of life of patients, slow disease progression and avoid disability.

1. Magliano DJ, Martin VJ, Owen AJ, Zomer E, Liew D. The productivity burden of diabetes at a population level. *Diabetes Care*. (2018) 41:979–84.
2. Livingstone SJ, Levin D, Looker HC, Lindsay RS, Wild SH, Joss N, et al. Estimated life expectancy in a Scottish cohort with type 1 diabetes, 2008–2010. *JAMA*. (2015) 313:37–44.
3. Bhatt DL, Steg PG, Ohman EM, Hirsch AT, Ikeda Y, Mas JL, Goto S, Liao CS, Richard AJ, Röther J, Wilson PW; REACH Registry Investigators. International prevalence, recognition, and treatment of cardiovascular risk factors in outpatients with atherothrombosis. *JAMA*. (2006);295:180–189.
4. Miller RG, Mahajan HD, Costacou T, Sekikawa A, Anderson SJ, Orchard TJ. A contemporary estimate of total mortality and cardiovascular disease risk in young adults with type 1 diabetes: the Pittsburgh epidemiology of diabetes complications study. *Diabetes Care*. (2016) 39:2296–303.
5. Sharma H, Lencioni M, Narendran P. Cardiovascular disease in type 1 diabetes. *Cardiovasc Endocrinol Metab*. (2019) 8:28–34.
6. Corbin KD, Driscoll KA, Pratley RE, Smith SR, Maahs DM, Mayer-Davis EJ. Obesity in type 1 diabetes: Pathophysiology, clinical impact, and mechanisms. *Endocr Rev*. (2018) 39:629–63.
7. Cai X, Li J, Cai W, Chen C, Ma J, Xie Z, et al. Meta-analysis of type 1 diabetes mellitus and risk of cardiovascular disease. *J Diabetes Complications*. (2021) 35:107833.
8. Bjornstad P, Donaghue KC, Maahs DM. Macrovascular disease and risk factors in youth with type 1 diabetes: time to be more attentive to treatment? *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol*. (2018) 6:809–20.
9. Foster NC, Beck RW, Miller KM, Clements MA, Rickels MR, DiMeglio LA, et al. State of type 1 diabetes management and outcomes from the T1D exchange in 2016–2018. *Diabetes Technol Ther*. (2019) 21:66–72.
10. Mehler PS, Coll JR, Estacio R, Esler A, Schrier RW, Hiatt WR. Intensive blood pressure control reduces the risk of cardiovascular events in patients with peripheral arterial disease and type 2 diabetes. *Circulation*. (2003);107:753–756.
11. Schäfer M, Nadeau KJ, Reusch JEB. Cardiovascular disease in young People with Type 1 Diabetes: Search for Cardiovascular Biomarkers. *J Diabetes Complications*. (2020) 34:107651.
12. Ference BA, Bhatt DL, Catapano AL, Packard CJ, Graham I, Kaptege S, et al. Association of genetic variants related to combined exposure to lower low-density lipoproteins and lower systolic blood pressure with lifetime risk of cardiovascular disease. *JAMA*. (2019) 322:1381–91.
13. Ward ZJ, Long MW, Resch SC, Giles CM, Cradock AL, Gortmaker SL. Simulation of growth trajectories of childhood obesity into adulthood. *N Engl J Med*. (2017) 377:2145–53
14. Phelan H, Foster NC, Schwandt A, Couper JJ, Willi S, Kroschwald P, et al. Longitudinal trajectories of BMI z-score: an international comparison of 11,513 Australian, American and German/Austrian/Luxembourgian youth with type 1 diabetes. *Pediatr Obes*. (2020) 15:e12582.
15. Liu L, Wang Z, Gong L, Zhang Y, Thijs L, Staessen JA, Wang J. Blood pressure reduction for the secondary prevention of stroke: a Chinese trial and a systematic review of the literature. *Hypertens Res*. (2009);32:1032–1040.
16. Sniderman AD, Lamarche B, Tilley J, Seccombe D, Frohlich J. Hypertriglyceridemic hyperapoB in type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care*. (2002);25:579–582.
17. Fornari E, Piona C, Rabbone I, Cardella F, Mozzillo E, Predieri B, et al. Cardiovascular risk factors in children and adolescents with type 1 diabetes in Italy: a multicentric observational study. *Pediatr Diabetes*. (2020) 21:1546–55.
18. Matsushita K, Coresh J, Sang Y, Chalmers J, Fox C, Guallar E, et al. Estimated glomerular filtration rate and albuminuria for prediction of cardiovascular outcomes: a collaborative meta-analysis of individual participant data. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol*. (2015) 3:514–25.
19. Anselmino M, Bartnik M, Malmberg K, Rydén L; Euro Heart Survey Investigators. Management of coronary artery disease in patients with and without diabetes mellitus: acute management reasonable but secondary prevention unacceptably poor: a report from the Euro Heart Survey on Diabetes and the Heart. *Eur J Cardiovasc Prev Rehabil*. (2007) 14:28–36.
20. Svane J, Lyng TH, Pedersen-Bjergaard U, Jespersen T, Gislason GH, Risgaard B, et al. Cause-specific mortality in children and young adults with diabetes mellitus: a danish nationwide cohort study. *Eur J Prev Cardiol*. (2019) 28:159–65.
21. Forbes JM, Fotheringham AK. Vascular complications in diabetes: old messages, new thoughts. *Diabetologia*. (2017) 60:2129–38.
22. Green JB, Bethel MA, Armstrong PW, Buse JB, Engel SS, Garg J, Josse R, Kaufman KD, Koglin J, Korn S, Lachin JM, McGuire DK, Pencina MJ, Standl E, Stein PP, Suryawanshi S, Van de Werf F, Peterson ED, Holman RR; TECOS Study Group. Effect of sitagliptin on cardiovascular outcomes in type 2 diabetes. *N Engl J Med*. (2015);373:232–242.